

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B266
Date: 06 Feb 2007
Take Off 10:03:10
Landing: 11:57:41
Flight Time 1h54m31

Campaign: VISURB - CIRRUS

Operating Area: South coast - Chilbolton

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Steve Ball	FAAM
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Dave Pollard	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
7	MARSS / FWVS	Chawn Harlow	Met Office
8	ARIES	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office
9	SWS	Martyn Glew	Met Office
10	CCM2 / Core Chem. / CVI	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
11	Mission Scientist 2	Simon Osborne	Met Office
12	AMS	Paul Williams	University Of Manchester
13	Filters	Alison Perry	FAAM
14	Cloud Physics	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B266 Track 06-FEB-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B266

Date:

Project:

Location:

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
094801		Start-Up	0.48 kft	103	
100310		T/O	0.47 kft	212	
100852		TWC	7.0 kft	357	power recycled - status 'on'
100948		ASP	7.0 kft	302	open
101257		TWC	9.1 kft	088	status - good
102119		JW	11.0 kft	068	zero check
102707		Video	11.0 kft	033	#1 dfc #2 ufc start
103020	104406	Profile 1	11.1 - 0.70 kft	327	
103650		P1	5.0 kft	329	interrupt fl50
103840		P1	5.0 kft	153	recommenced
104220		qnh	1.6 kft	149	1003
104259		P1	1.2 kft	153	500ft/min
104441	111030	Run 1	0.69 - 1.0 kft	118	
104513		qnh	0.72 kft	113	1006
104545		R1	0.67 kft	112	start@ wp 87
104622		bbr	0.73 kft	111	retract
104725		Heimann	0.70 kft	112	cal 06
105608		R1	0.72 kft	168	track change to avoid weather
105953		R1	1.2 kft	162	climbing to 1300ft weather avoidance
110029		R1	1.7 kft	169	1500ft on qnh
110150		R1	1.3 kft	204	profile back to 500ft
110314		R1	0.69 kft	193	500ft
110722		R1	1.1 kft	193	adjusting to 900ft, weather
111104		!	1.2 kft	330	end science
111823		Heimann	8.1 kft	356	closed, cal 06
114402		ASP	13.9 kft	201	closed
115741		Land	0.51 kft	213	Cranfield
120449		Shutdown	0.51 kft	305	

B266 Track 06-FEB-07

FAAM Sortie Brief

Objective #1: VISURB UK. Assessment of aerosol properties related to visibility
Objective #2: in-situ and remote sensing of aircraft induced cirrus over Chilbolton

Flight No: B266

Date: 06 February 2007

Trial objectives:

To carry out in-situ sampling of aerosol properties and their effect on radiation and to make in-situ and remote sensing measurements of aircraft induced (or natural) cirrus over Chilbolton.

Location:

- #1. Off the east and south coast of the UK (e.g. AMPEP points 46 to 80, clockwise around the coast).
- #2. Area close to Chilbolton (Routing points 12 to 15).

Weather:

High loadings of atmospheric aerosols for #1. Aviation induced cirrus for #2.

Special requirements:

Check the mesoscale model forecast for the position of aerosol plumes before flying.

Instruments of particular importance:

Nephelometer/Wet-nephelometer

AMS

Cloud physics: PCASP x2, SID-1, SID-2, CDP.

CVI

BBRs

SWS/SHIMS

ARIES

MARSS

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST SHOULD NOTE FORMATION OF ANY CONTRAILS. Rear video camera should be used.

For VISURB: when at 500ft, SWS should look upwards.

For CIRRUS: when above the Ci, SWS and ARIES should look downwards, and when below the Ci SWS and ARIES should look upwards.

CVI should be in aerosol mode for VISURB, and in CVI mode when in cirrus.

Flight pattern (note times are for guidance purposes only), AMPEP points should be used for planning purposes:

1. Take off from Cranfield at 10:00Z.
2. Transit to northernmost AMPEP point (current forecast suggests the vicinity of Flamborough Head (AMPEP point 80), but this may change as the forecast is currently uncertain, Figure 1) and perform a profile descent at 1000ft/minute to 500ft in a southerly direction [40mins, T=40mins].
3. Perform a long SLR at 500ft heading southwards around the coast. [80mins, T=120mins].
4. Where concentrations of atmospheric aerosols are high, mark point X and break the SLR, and perform three additional reciprocal runs of 5 minutes duration at 1000ft, 2500ft, and 5000ft [20mins, T=140mins].

5. Reposition the aircraft to point X at 500ft [5mins, T=145mins]
 6. Continue the 500ft run around the coast (AMPEP point 46 reached).
 7. Descend to 50ft, then perform profile ascent from 50ft to FL330 or above the cirrus [30mins, T=175mins].
 8. If cirrus cloud is present then engage the contrail portion of the flight. Otherwise recover to Cranfield.
 9. ---- End of VISURB portion of flight ----
 10. ---- Start of Chilbolton part of flight ----
 11. Perform a 15 minute run **above** any cirrus orientated approximately E/W with the easternmost point at Chilbolton. Routing points 15 to 12 have been suggested as suitable positions [15mins, T=190mins].
 12. Descend into any cirrus and perform a 15minute run **within** the cirrus in E/W orientation 20mins,T=210mins].
 13. Descend to below the cirrus and perform a 15minute run **below** the cirrus in E/W orientation 20mins,T=210mins].
 14. If the BAe146 is contrailing, then reposition and perform a shallow banked orbit at ~20degrees angle of bank to make a 'contrail doughnut' [15mins, T=225mins].
 15. Continue orbiting sampling the contrail doughnut for approximately 3 more orbits [15mins, T=240mins].
 16. Repeat points 11-13.
 17. Recover to Cranfield [5hours duration total]
- Aerosol

At 12Z on 6/ 2/2007, from 03Z on 5/ 2/2007

Figure 1. Forecast of aerosol for 12Z on 6th November, 2007. The approximate area of operation for the VISURB portion of the flight is shown in the solid black line. The Grey line shows the Chilbolton portion of the flight.

Mission Scientist Debrief

B266

6th February 2007

David Pollard

The aim of the sortie was to conduct measurements of aerosol and pollution around the south coast of England with an additional aim of investigating cirrus over Chilbolton at the end of the sortie.

Weather: A slack Col was situated over the country resulting in a very weak northerly flow. Initial tephis indicated that Ci conditions were very unlikely and this was backed up by satellite imagery early on in the sortie and so the Ci part of the sortie was abandoned early on.

There were variable amounts of cloud at medium levels with some embedded showers.

Sortie: After transiting out at FL110, a stepped profile descent was undertaken northwards from point 87, broken at FL50 in order to arrive back at point 87 at 500 ft. the northern end of this manoeuvre was under clear skies with a significant bank of cloud over the East Anglia coast. On the return leg of the profile, a distinct, narrow layer of pollution could be seen to the West, and some chemistry and aerosol instruments responded to this.

A run was then started around the East Anglia coast, but it quickly became evident that instrument problems were going to force an early end to the sortie. Therefore the run was continued in order to reduce the fuel load before recovering to Cranfield.

Mission Scientist's Log

POWLAN

Flight No **B.13266**

Date 6/2/2

Page 1 of 2

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
9:44					EGTC, Wx v 7/8 St clear above
10:02:30					T/O
10:06		FL50			Just below base of broken
					St / Sc, Heavy below
					2 layers of cl. upper @ v 8kft
10:20					Broken below coming into
					old bank.
10:30:20	P1	110	326		@ vt 87 hdg N. in cld,
					clearer to W
10:31:30					and of cld, some drizzle
					fair vis below & around.
					POAST noisy,
10:36					1/8 above some Cu to E
					good vis
10:36:50	P1	500A			P1 interrupted, turning S
					Moving to S. U E
10:38:40	P1	50	S		Resume
					V. distinct return
					Layer to E at crest
					left v. thin
10:42		1000A			500 ft/min
10:44:06	P1	500A			End. ^{O3} dropping
					Depth signal
10:44:44	P1				NOx below 3kft
					under cloud v. deep in

to S poss thinning ahead to E

Poluvar

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.266**

Date **6/2/7**

Page **2** of **2**

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:52					Neph display frozen GRM(?) inst U/S PCASP(?) rubbish
10:53					turning S at Pt 40 Some showers to S
10:55:					turning L. to avoid shower
					Science terminated due to inst problems at point 41 returning via outbound track at med level.
					Apart from plume of pollution (source unclear?) encountered during initial descent and 1st run nothing significant to report multiple inst failure resulted in early termination of sortie.
11:53					Encountering layer of pollution at ~ 25ft to h.

SWS and SHIMS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B266** Date **06/02/07** Operat or(s) **M. GLEW** log page **1** of **3**

Note to operator: Indicate whether entry refers to SWS or SHIMS

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	S W S	U S H	L S H
				Vis	NIR				
						PRB TAKE OFF. USA SHUTTER NOT WORKING on LABVIEW. WORKS ON DIAG-EXE. DIAG-EXE has SWS on 0, USA on 3, LSA on 2. All refers to URS modules, no SR modules.			
1004						TRANSFER NAD			
101420						TRANSFER ZEN(46°)			
10444	R1	500'	+6	200			✓		
				250				✓	
				1000					✓
1050						SHUTTER PROBLEMS. CLOUD ABOUT			
1056						SWS, LSA SHUTTERS OK USA. WHEN USA DIAG-EXE CAN OPEN SHUT USA SHUTTER. IF USE LABVIEW FOR RECORD DARK IT OPENS USA SHUTTER			
1100						FREZER TEMP +7°C. ROTIF PELTERS ON			
110440	R1	500'	+6	100			✓		
1106						IF ON STATUS PANEL SET USA SHUTTERS TO 4, SWS SHUTTERS TO 1, LSA SHUTTERS TO 3, SHUTTERS WORK FROM LABVIEW			
11000						500			✓
11104						END SCIENCE, AERUSOL INSTRUMENTS			
1120						TEMP OF FREEZER +1°C, ALL WORKING.			

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	06/02/07	Flight	B266	log pages
Operator(s)	Chawn Harlow		Campaign	WINTEX		
Departure	Cranfield		Arrival	Cranfield		

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•
FERA on	at time					
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	°C	Ch	°C	Ch18	°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on	at time					
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)	at time					
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		•

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software	at time					
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
Deimos NOT operated	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time			
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	345	Cold	275	
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	
		33	37.5	40	42.4	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again	at time					
						09:51:
						27

Flight:

B266

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevezorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Report Created 15/03/2007
12:08:00

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

06/02/2007 12:54:44

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B266

Date: 06 Feb 2007

Instruments

Grim u/s

New pcasp noisy

Old pcasp noisy

Wet neph u/s

Dry neph u/s

Heimann cals ????

Aircraft

Satcom-H Calls

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 07/2/07

Flight No: 8266

Pre-Flighter: A.M.W

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
Aircraft Cabin: Power-up				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	NO GASES
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	INA WOULDNT ALIGN UNTIL CB RESET!
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up	NOT FITTED
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	CAL OK - UNDER PLATFORM 57 24°C
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	NOT FITTED
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	u/s
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
Proceed to External Checks				
External Checks overleaf →				

Pre-Flighter's Log

<u>No.</u>	<u>√ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<u>External Checks</u>				
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nezvorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
40	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				Signed
43	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ICEX applied		
45	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a) Nil (b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more
46	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B266:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics In Flight	On SID2 PC which is in Germany
Cloud Physics Processing	Awaiting processing completion
Filters	no log taken - training flight with no science filters exposed
Core Chemistry	pre flight only, unmanned operation on auto calibrate so no In Flight log
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	22 Mar 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

- 1 x Upward Facing Camera (info taken from Flight Summary)
- 1 x Downward Facing Camera (info taken from Flight Summary)

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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